

The impact of perceived organizational support and extrinsic motivation on job satisfaction: The mediating role of intrinsic motivation

Mehboob Alam^{1,*}, Fozia Gul¹, Syed Intasar Hussain Kazmi²

- ^{1.} The Institute of Management Sciences, Pak AIMS, Lahore
^{2.} The Superior University, Lahore, Pakistan.
^{*} Corresponding Author: mbadawn@gmail.com

Article Information	Abstract
<p>Article history: Submitted: 17 January, 2023 Accepted: 01 May, 2023 Published: 30th June, 2023</p>	<p><i>The current study holds the object of exploring the mediating role of intrinsic motivation between perceived organizational support, extrinsic motivation & job satisfaction. Data from 340 employees in the manufacturing sector were collected to test the hypothesis. Results presented that POS has a strong impact on employee job satisfaction & extrinsic motivation, as well as satisfaction on the job. Moreover, constructive effects regarding the mediating position of intrinsic drive between POS & extrinsic motivation and job satisfaction. An individual is intrinsically motivated when an association takes care of efforts and employee's well-being, such support becomes a channel for better and positive outcomes for employees.</i></p>
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Introduction

In the recent decade, the manufacturing sector of Pakistan is growing very fast and facing many challenges regarding employee dissatisfaction, turnover, welfare & low productivity/performance. Perceived organizational support refers to awareness of employees regarding the degree to which association value their donations and be concerned about their well-being” (Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison, & Sowa, 1986, p. 501). Perceived organizational support is a key factor that can help overcome these challenges. The perceived organizational support concept stands on organizational support theory. This theory is explaining how employees contribute to the organization when the organization support and values their employees. The perceived organizational support has two components one is procedural justice and the other is supervisory support. When the employee got procedural justice, they are doing good for the

organization, and in the same way, when the supervisory support is also from the supervisor, the employee does good for the organization. As a result, the employee's performance increased.

For attaining sustainable competitive advantage, satisfied, motivated employees and enhance performance are key drivers for organizational success. It is very important to consider the approaches that best-fit employees related needs. Research highlights factors regarding work outcomes and jobs to develop organizational performance (Nguyen et al., 2014; Ahmad et al., 2014). To progress the manufacturing sector of Pakistan and its system for quality work, new research is required to enhance employee satisfaction with the job for organizational performance.

To meet the challenges of this sector, it is necessary that employee has to be satisfied. For this purpose, the employees can be motivated through extrinsic motivation. The extrinsic drive is "engaging in activities that lead to some known/external reward" (Ryan & Deci, 2000b, p. 55). Extrinsic motivation is included different rewards, such as bonuses, dividends, promotion opportunities, salary increases, education & job training, staff traveling allowance, allowance, prize, etc.

The rationale of this paper is to discover the effect of perceived organizational support & extrinsic inspiration on job satisfaction. Firstly, perceived organizational support outcome would be explored through the mediating role of intrinsic(inherent) incentive and second, extrinsic motivation impact would be explored through the mediating role of intrinsic motivation resting on job satisfaction.

The present study is the researcher's attempt for updating information for leaders of management/sciences & organizational behavior that perceived organizational support, motivated employees, and job satisfaction affect the quality of work and organizational performance as a whole. In organizations to obtain a competitive advantage, satisfied employees are important assets that accomplish this goal, particularly, in the manufacturing sector which show public relation satisfaction level. Additionally, it could support organizations/businesses to get the desired objectives. Asian industries are facing losses in terms of finance, unsatisfied human capital, and work environment, so there is a need for new research for the betterment & awareness of employees and leaders to get the best and quality work outcomes Leghari (2003). This study is an attempt to trigger new ways for organizations and employees to understating challenging matters and enable them to cope with them. It is indicated that POS, IM & EM would help to improve job satisfaction and when organizations het satisfied employees it will lead them to better and quality performance of an overall organization.

Theoretical Perspective

Perceived Organizational Support and intrinsic motivation

The basis for the perception of organizational support lies in organizational support theory (OST) and social exchange theory (SET). Organizational support theory has developed by Eisenberger in 1986. The theory described employees' common beliefs about an organization in the context of worth their socio-emotional (affiliation, social support & esteem) well-being and contribution, as well as how much their devotion and performance are being rewarded (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Perceived organizational support (POS) refers to "a careful collaboration or support that necessitates to effectively execute the job." Hakkak and Ghodsi (2013). Organizational support theory is based on two principles, that is employee and supervisor. From the employee's perceptive, he/she contributes to the institution, and from the supervisor's perceptive, they take action like an agent of the organization (Eisenberger et al, 1986: Levinson, 1965). It is indicated by Kurtessis et al., (2017) that when the degree of POS is high, the efforts of

employees will also be high, it indicates a reciprocal relationship between employee and organization.

It is indicated by (Deci et al., 2017) that intrinsic motivation compacts with performance activity that is related to natural satisfaction, meaning, such satisfaction display employee enjoyment and interest in job tasks instead of other reasons i.e., reward/appreciation (Olafsen et al.,2015). Intrinsically motivated individuals react positively to jobs inherently and involve their interest, contribution, and satisfied feeling (Amabileetal.,1996; Decietal.,2012; Olafsenetal.,2015). Feelings of employees are important as when they experience their institute carefully regarding their well-being, they are ultimately motivated intrinsically & their contribution towards their job and organization is constructive in terms of efforts, interest, and curiosity. Such positive behavior of motivated employees leads to better performance and take keen responsibility for job-related tasks and organization, thereby producing job satisfaction. Hence, based on the above, hypothesized relation is:

H₁: POS is positively related to intrinsic motivation

Intrinsic motivation and job satisfaction

Inherent (intrinsic) motivation includes an emotional component (enjoyment of task) and an intellectual factor (to seek challenge) (Deci and Ryan, 2012). As per CET persons taking an interest in challenges, are mentally strong and acknowledge engagement towards their tasks with helpful behavior and more responsibility. On the other hand, those who are concerned with task enjoyment produce only specific tasks of being rewarded& compensated (Deci and Ryan, 2012). Two-factor theory of Herzberg (1966) (i.e., motivation and satisfaction), the major drivers for the satisfaction of employees are factors in which employee is working and engaged to complete their tasks i.e., internal work environment. Such factors are known as motivations, as they not only become an active source of employee motivation but also enhance the motivation of already motivated employees, to better put their efforts & gain improved performance (Hackman and Oldham, 1976).

Consequently, drivers of motivation possibly enhance the work-related motivation of employees (Ford, 1969), for the ultimate result of job satisfaction. A close association is found by Millette and Gagné, (2008) regarding voluntary satisfaction/motivation and features of job. It is also confirmed by Clary et al., 1998 that motivation is an enhanced projecting function in shaping voluntary satisfaction. It is also endorsed noteworthy influence of inside motivation & loyalty on satisfaction because it leads to high satisfaction in a job and less intention to job leave (Lee et al., 2014). A strong association has been found by Reeser et al. (2005) between satisfaction & volunteer enthusiasm that is external/internal aspects & morals). As a conclusion, there is a positive connection between motivation & performance. Better performance is subject to necessary abilities & capabilities and high inspiration (Babaei et al., 2015). The succeeding hypothesis is specified:

H₂: Intrinsic Motivation drive is absolutely connected to job satisfaction.

Perceived Organizational Support and job satisfaction

It is clarified by Armstrong-Stassen (1998) that the behavior of employees is affected by their beliefs regarding basic procedures that establish their organization & POS is one of them. Past researchers [Cropanzano et al,1997; Filipova A.A. (2010); Erdogan B, Enders J (2007) discovered a strong association between job satisfaction and POS. It is suggested by Armstrong-Stassen (1998), in their study that supervisors with a high degree of organizational support, stated

a high level of job satisfaction, compared to those who receive a low intensity of POS-perceived organizational support. Meaning that POS develops employee trust & opinions regarding organizations that acknowledge and reward struggles in achieving better performance Rhoades L, Eisenberger R (2002). It is revealed by past research that POS is an exchange process socially, which reciprocate relations & action of organization and employees. In this exchange process, employees feel accountable for the upkeep organization in achieving its objectives, leading to better compensation. According to social exchange theory, employees being psychologically attached to an organization feels that his/her contributions are acknowledged, which leads to fostering association among them Biswas, S., Bhatnagar, J. (2013). Subsequently, employees respond to organizational support in several positive ways and they are more satisfied with their job duties. Individuals with organizational support, psychologically and intrinsically feel an obligation to be attached to work & organization keenly. Thereby, employees are more satisfied and loyal to the organization & job tasks (Gillet et al, 2013). Based on the above discussion, a third hypothesis is proposed that:

H₃: Perceived Organizational Support is definitely linked to satisfaction of job.

Mediating effect of Intrinsic motivation between Perceived Organizational Support and job satisfaction

Based on the hypothesized model, it is inferred built-in inspiration (IM) mediates affiliation b/w job satisfaction & POS. IM is a noteworthy driver for satisfaction at a job. instrument of CET (cognitive evaluation theory) (Deci and Ryan, 1985) is used in Current inquiry, to check the mediating role of intrinsic motivation in the association b/w satisfaction of job & POS. As per CET (cognitive them in their work responsibilities with respect ensure quality relationship (Eisenberger and Stinglhamber, 2011), meaning that such association stimulates independence evaluation theory), organizations who are concerned regarding employees well- being and support (Deci and Ryan, 2012 Hirschler et al., 2014). Reinforcement of the perception of employees regarding valuable treatment is done through POS (Colquitt et al., 2013). Support from organizations motivates employees intrinsically to better exercise job responsibilities with dedication& trust which leads them toward job satisfaction, so, the research hypothesis is:

H₄: Intrinsic motivation mediates affiliation between Perceived Organizational Support and job satisfaction.

Extrinsic & intrinsic motivation with satisfaction of job

Differentiation between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is explained in SDT by (Ryan et al, 1985; Deci et al, 2002). Intrinsic motivation is integrally self-directed whereas extrinsic motivation is based on a range organized to independent (i.e., controlled to autonomous) (Ryan and Deci, 2000). The level of autonomy includes choice in work, on the other hand, control encompasses the feeling of pressure in work employees engage (Gagné and Deci, 2005).

Employees who have controlled motivation are measured by external rules. Deci and Ryan, 1985 indicated that supervisors that are externally planned focused on punishment and reward, which include security of the job, advancement & avoid job loss. Internally motivated leaders experience moral values, due to the fact that they are responsible for being honest with employees, as this is their duty, if they do not exercise such behavior at work, they feel awkward (Gagné et al., 2015).

Integrated rules & intrinsic motivation fall under autonomous motivation. Acknowledged supervisors/leaders are more effective as they exhibit and see the worth of moral leadership (Ryan

and Deci, 2002). Leaders that are integrated display being respectable leader as it conveys their goals in life and carries satisfaction (Gagné and Deci, 2005). Lastly, inherently motivated leaders become active as they experience adequate, pleasant & motivating leadership (Gagné and Deci, 2005). The degree of direction may vary and impact differently as leaders behave differently, so perceptions of employees/followers may differ about leadership style (Gagné and Deci, 2005). Transformational leadership by Bass's (1990) presented important suggestions for positive results for both individuals & organizations (see Barling et al., 2011 for analysis). There are four dimensions of transformational leadership style (Bass, 1985): idealizing influence (doing the right thing); inspiring motivation (boosting employees for achieving performance levels outside their expectations); intellectual motivation (giving challenges to employees about problems in innovative ways; and personalized deliberation (support employees' needs). Employees who are intrinsically and extrinsically motivated will be more engaged in work duties and satisfied with the job.

Transformational leadership has a Constructive impact on job satisfaction and commitment of employees (Bono and Judge, 2003). Such positive results occur due to the autonomy leaders provide to their followers (Gagné and Deci (2005), therefore employees contribute accordingly. It is also referred by Bas (1985), various styles of leadership are the exchange process between employee and leader. Transactional leadership is lacking leadership and only responded to undesirable behaviors and provide reward or punishment according to performance. Pleased employees who are intrinsically motivated will lead to extrinsic motivation, which results in their satisfaction at work. So, supporting the exceeding argument we projected:

H₅: Extrinsic (external) motivation is surely connected toward intrinsic motivation

H₆: External (extrinsic) motivation certainly associated with work satisfaction

H₇: Intrinsic motivation mediates between extrinsic motivation & job Satisfaction

Research Methodology

Sample and Procedural

The population of the current study consists serving employees of the shoe manufacturing sector, in Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan. The population includes all the employees of the administration, finance, sales, marketing, and production departments. For this study, the questionnaire survey method was used for the current study. With a questionnaire survey, we measure the influence of POS-perceived organizational and external drive (EM) on job satisfaction through mediating job of intrinsic incentive. Simple random probability sampling methods carry out for the collection of data for the current study. A total number of 376 questionnaire surveys was distributed among the employees' shoe manufacturing sector. 340 respondents (90%) completed and return the questionnaire survey and 30 respondents (8%) did not return the questionnaire survey and 20 (5%) respondents' data were incomplete.

In total 340 respondents, 109 (33%) were female and 231 (67%) were male respondents. The majority of the respondents belong to a scale ranging from 17-19 which were 221(65%) of the total respondents. Of the respondents, 168 had ages ranging from 31-40(49.4%). Respondents 124 (36.5%) were experienced ranging from 0-5. Of the respondents, 229 (67%) were married and 111(33%) were unmarried.

Measures

All the measures used in the current study were adopted by different scholars. Study variables included Perceived organizational support, ethical leadership, extrinsic motivation, and job satisfaction. These were calculated on the 5x Likert range (1-Strongly Disagree, 2- Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree, 5- Strongly agree) except control variables.

Perceived organizational Support

Eisenberger et al. (1997) eight items scale was used to measure POS (Perceived organizational support). A sample item was “My association concern about my opinions”. Cronbach’ α for measure 0.728.

Extrinsic Motivation

Extrinsic drive is measured using Ryan & Connell, (1989) three items scale. A sample item was “My supervisor can be trusted”. Cronbach’ α for the measure 0.827.

Intrinsic Motivation

Intrinsic drive (motivation) is measured using Ryan & Connell, (1989) two items scale. An example item was “I enjoy the work itself”. Cronbach’s α for the measure was 0.809.

Job Satisfaction

Satisfaction of job calculated by Sakes, (2006), 3x items scale. A sample item was “In general, I like working here”. Cronbach’s α for the measure was 0.737

Control Variables

Control variables include, gender, pay scale, experience, and marital status. These were not part of the conceptual model, but these affected the study variables. These were used as control variables. The data for these were collected along with the study variables. The Male was coded as 1 and the female was coded as 2, pay scale (1-4, 5-11, 12-16,17-20), age (21-30, 31-40, 41-50, 51-60), experience (0-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20, 21-25, 26-30, 31 & above) marital status coded as 1 married and 2 unmarried.

Analysis of Data Approaches

SPSS - Statistical Package for social sciences 24 was used to examine the descriptive statistics which included reliability, frequencies, mean, standard deviation, and correlation analysis. To test the hypotheses PROCESS macros (Hayes & Preacher, 2013) has been used. There were two mediations in the current study. First, the mediation form included (H1-H4) & second mediation model include (H5-H7). Analysis of moment structure (AMOS) 24 was used for confirmatory factor analysis.

Results

Descriptive Analysis

Mean, standard deviation, correlation, and reliability of the study variables (perceived organizational support, extrinsic motivation, intrinsic (inherent) motivation, and satisfaction at the job) in addition to control variables (gender, pay scale, age, experience & marital status) have been shown in Table 1. Extrinsic motivation reliability is 0.827 and perceived organizational reliability is 0.827 maximum & minimum, respectively. Perceived organizational support is positively & significantly associated with intrinsic motivation ($r=0.375$, $p<.01$), and job satisfaction ($r=0.524$, $p<.01$). Extrinsic motivation is connected with intrinsic motivation ($r=0.286$, $p<.01$), job satisfaction ($r=0.639$, $p<.01$). Correlation analysis provides initial support to our hypothesis.

Figure No.1: PROPOSED MODEL

Table 1: Correlations

Variables	Mean	S. D	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Gender	1.68	.467	1								
2. Pay Scale	3.46	.817	.497**	1							
3. Age	1.87	.817	.046	.364**	1						
4. Experience	2.25	1.365	-.074	.281**	.775**	1					
5. Marital Status	1.33	.470	.102	-.133*	-.366**	-.324**	1				
6. POS	3.31	.557	.074	.168**	.150**	.044	-.040	1			
7. EM	3.70	.769	.067	.074	.071	.027	.020	.560**	1		
8. IM	3.89	.756	.117*	.172**	.205**	.204**	-.023	.375**	.286**	1	
9. JS	3.63	.725	.187**	.266**	.142**	.081	-.038	.524**	.639**	.350**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Hypothesis testing

Confirmatory factor analysis was done by using AMOS 24 to check the goodness of the models of the study variables before the testing of the hypothesis. In the current study measurement model was compared with the alternative models. But the results of the measurement model are a good fit. According to statistical analysis and best-fit values of the measurement model CFI=0.921, GFI=0.916, TLI=0.898 RMSEA=0.080 & RMR=0.041.

Table 2: Hypothesis

Model	X ²	Df	X ² /df	CFI	GFI	TLI	RMSEA	RMR
Measurement Model	225.205	71	3.172	0.921	0.916	0.898	0.080	0.041
Model-1 POS- (EM & JS)	225.576	53	4.256	0.895	0.897	0.869	0.098	0.046
Model-2 POS- (IM & JS)	269.536	43	6.268	0.823	0.874	0.774	0.125	0.054
Model-3 POS- (EM & IM)	323.801	43	7.530	0.803	0.853	0.748	0.139	0.067
Model-4 POS-(EM-IM-JS)	459.227	76	6.042	0.803	0.837	0.764	0.122	0.059

N=340, X² = Chi-Square, df= Degree of Freedom, CFI= Comparative Fit Index,

TLI= Tucker Lewis Index, GFI=Goodness of Fit Index,

RMSEA= root-mean-square error of approximation, RMR= Root mean square residual.

Model-1= Perceived organizational support and merged extrinsic motivation & job satisfaction as one factor

Model-2= Perceived organizational support and merged intrinsic motivation & job satisfaction as one factor

Model-3= Perceived organizational support and merged extrinsic & intrinsic motivation as one factor

Model-4= Perceived organizational support and merged extrinsic, intrinsic motivation & job satisfaction as one factor

In Tables 3 & 4, to test the hypothesis of the study variables, researchers implement Andrew F. Hayes' PROCESS Macro model 4 (Hayes&Preacher,2013). The hypothesis outcome showed in Table 3 & table 4. The consequences of the SPSS PROCESS macro indicated, perceived organizational support considerably influences intrinsic motivation ($\beta=0.509$, $t=7.433$, $p<0.000$),

so supported H1 (figure 2 'path a'). Intrinsic motivation also positively & significantly impacts job satisfaction ($\beta=0.171$, $t=3.635$, $p<0.000$) when controlling perceived organizational support (path b in figure 2). Perceived organizational support indicated a constructive effect on the satisfaction of the job ($\beta=0.595$, $t=9.308$, $p<0.000$) after calculating intrinsic motivation (in figure 2 c' path). These results were supported by H2 & H4. The results specified total effect of perceived organizational support on job satisfaction was positive and significant ($\beta=0.682$, $t=11.307$, $p<0.000$), so supported H3.

Furthermore, the findings of the mediation model (simple) proposed, perceived organizational support is having an indirect result towards job satisfaction by intrinsic motivation. The indirect effect was ($\beta=0.087$) and 2x-tailed significance for standard distribution showed that the indirect outcome was significant (Sobel $z=3.242$, $p>0.000$). The bootstrapping result was consisting of Sobel 95% CI (0.035, 0.161) about an indirect outcome (ab) having a non-zero point. Thus, H4 favored.

Table 3: Results of Simple Mediation Model

Variables	B	SE	t	P		
Direct and Total Effect						
Job Satisfaction regressed on POS	0.682	0.06	11.307	0.000		
Intrinsic Motivation regressed on POS	0.509	0.068	7.433	0.000		
Job Satisfaction regressed on Intrinsic Motivation controlling POS	0.171	0.047	3.635	0.000		
Job Satisfaction regressed on POS controlling Intrinsic Motivation	0.595	0.064	9.308	0.000		
	Value	SE	LL CI95%	UL CI95%	Z	P
Indirect effect and significance using the normal distribution						
Sobel	0.087	0.027	.035	.161	3.242	0.001
	ME	SE	LL CI 95%	UL CI 95%	Z	P
Bootstrap results for indirect effect						
Effect	0.087	0.027	.035	.161	3.242	0.001

Note: N = 340. β = Unstandardized Regression Coefficient; SE = Standard Error; Bootstrap Sample Size = 1000;

LL = Lower Limit; CI = Confidence Interval; UL = Upper Limit, 1,000 Bootstrapping

Furthermore, findings indicated that extrinsic motivation significantly impacts intrinsic motivation ($\beta=0.281$, $t=5.489$, $p<0.000$), so holds H5 (path 'a' -figure 2). Intrinsic motivation has a positive & significant impact on job satisfaction ($\beta=0.174$, $t=4.268$, $p<0.000$) while manipulating extrinsic drive (figure 3, path 'b'). The extrinsic incentive has a positive impact on job satisfaction ($\beta=0.445$, $t=13.794$, $p<0.000$) when controlling intrinsic motivation (c' path in figure 3). Extrinsic motivation positively and significantly impacts job satisfaction (c in a path in figure 3) which support H6. Moreover, in H7, the indirect relation between extrinsic motivation and job satisfaction was positive ($\beta=0.049$) and significant (Sobel $Z=3.335$, $p<0.000$). Results verified Sobel's check because 95% CI (.021, 0.094) about the indirect effect (ab) does not include zero. So, H7 was supported.

Discussion

The results of the existing study specify the intensity of perceived organizational support importance, its background, and predictable outcomes. The empirical results of the study revealed the well-built relationship between POS among intrinsic motivation & JS (job satisfaction) and contribute to an existing body of literature. Particularly, the current study is a distinctive effort to examine POS, EM as the background of IM & job satisfaction as its outcomes from the Asian perspective. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, the current paper is essential due to reality as is unique and former research that carries out the straight effect of POS & EM lying on IM, job satisfaction. Moreover, inspect IM mediation b/w POS, JS also b/w EM & job satisfaction in the shoe manufacturing sector of Lahore, Pakistan. The results of the study supported our hypothesized framework.

Table 4: Results of Simple Mediation Model

Variables	B	SE	t	P		
Direct and Total Effect						
Job Satisfaction regressed on EM	0.603	0.039	15.285	0.000		
Intrinsic Motivation regressed on EM	0.281	0.051	5.489	0.000		
Job Satisfaction regressed on Intrinsic Motivation controlling EM	0.174	0.041	4.268	0.000		
Job Satisfaction regressed on EM controlling Intrinsic Motivation	0.554	0.040	13.794	0.000		
	Value	SE	LLCI 95%	ULCI 95%	Z	P
Indirect effect and significance using the normal distribution						
Sobel	0.049	0.015	.021	.094	3.335	0.001
	ME	SE	LLCI 95%	ULCI 95%	Z	P

Bootstrap results for indirect effect						
Effect	0.049	0.015	.021	.094	3.335	0.001

Note: N = 340. β = Unstandardized Regression Coefficient; SE = Standard Error; Bootstrap Sample Size = 1000;

Figure No.2. Indirect effect of perceived organizational support on job satisfaction through extrinsic motivation.

Figure No.3 Indirect effect of perceived ethical leadership on job satisfaction through extrinsic motivation.

Firstly, the findings of the research showed, POS- Perceived Organizational Support- is absolutely and notably interconnected to intrinsic motivation. Perceived Organizational Support indicates a main role in motivating employees for better outputs which ultimately results in achieving the goals and objectives of employees towards their job. Perceived Organizational Support participate a significant position in the satisfaction of employees, it provides guidance toward employees in terms of facilitating a motivated workforce (Kurtessis et al., (2017) and effective results for an organization.

Secondly, results suggested that IM (intrinsic motivation) positively allied to job satisfaction. Employees who are intrinsically motivated will produce effective results for the organization, it indicates satisfaction of employees regarding their job and organization and hence motivated intrinsically (Babaei et al., 2015). The empirical results proved; intrinsic motivation is important and leads employees to job satisfaction.

Thirdly, the Results of our study revealed that perceived organizational support, and employee satisfaction at job positively connected. Perceived organizational support) important to get a satisfied workforce because if employees know their values of care and recognition which is accounted for by the organization, employees will be more satisfied. Support regarding preceding studies, the conclusion of the current paper empirically confirmed when organizations value employees and care for their well-being, they are more satisfied and motivated (Gillet et al, 2013).

Fourthly, the results of this study illustrate intrinsic(basic) inspiration mediation affiliation among perceived organizational support & job satisfaction. Intrinsically motivated employees feel energetic, encouraged, and independent toward their tasks/jobs. Such employees are ready to get challenges in terms of responsibilities and can achieve desired results effectively through helping and motivating others at the workplace as described by many researchers (Hirschler et al., 2014).

Fifthly, our study results revealed that extrinsic motivation is positively related to intrinsic motivation. In the recently growing world, extrinsic reward adds value and recognition to employees' performance and is an important predictor for organizational success in terms of a satisfied workforce. Additionally, empirical results of the study showed that employees who are extrinsically motivated along with intrinsic motivation apply new ideas and skill variety which increase their motivation level for better performance as described by different authors.

Lastly, we found that intrinsic motivation mediates the connection linking extrinsic motivation & job satisfaction. Intrinsically motivated individuals create a sense of obligation and responsibility towards organizations as they know that their organization value and care about their well-being. Employees motivated intrinsically feel motivated, and energetic towards their job and also promote job satisfaction because when employees are intrinsically motivated, they establish more interest and accountability and turn into more occupied and satisfied (Barling et al., 2011).

Theoretical Contribution

Present paper supplement to the existing literature of POS in numerous conducts. Foremost, the current study provides offered literature regarding POS through experience to explore POS (IM) history & results. Preceding studies focused on the results and suggested investigating the contextual and other motivational factors that could make possible POS in turn to improve understanding of feature that support it. After this, the current attempt inspects POS and EM as contributors to IM and job satisfaction as its outcome. The empirical results of the study give support to the observation that POS and extrinsically motivated employees stimulate a positive work environment and motivation which they get from supervisors/organizations and boost inspiration and zeal which help in job satisfaction.

Second, empirical results authenticate the positive association between IM and JS, it offers confirmation of the important outcomes of IM as recommended by different authors (Babaei et al., 2015). The individual is intrinsically motivated when an association takes care of efforts and employee well-being, such support becomes the channel for better and positive outcomes for employees (attitude, behavior, and performance) (Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002).

Third, the current study discovered the mediating relationship between POS and JS and between EM and JS to clarify how and why employees are motivated at work.

Fourth, the relationship between POS and JS in addition to EM and JS is experienced empirically and established from the organizational perspective. Ahmed et al 2013 signify, the greater the organizations involved in valuing and caring for the well-being of employees, the higher the employees will be satisfied, as POS is a replacement process among individuals & organizations. Job satisfaction is the direction to cultivate a support approach from an organization (Baran et al., 2012). In addition, the extrinsic motivation that employees get from their organizations fosters their level of motivation towards their job tasks in a more satisfying manner. (Hirschler et al., 2014).

Practical Contribution

The current study establishes significant implications for manufacturing sector administration and practitioners. This study views POS & extrinsic motivation as important predictors of intrinsic motivation(drive) and job satisfaction. POS (perceived organizational support) and extrinsic inspiration both have optimistic and major impact lying on job satisfaction in the manufacturing sector. During a competitive scenario, the employment atmosphere is vibrant, organization is striving for the satisfaction of their most valuable asset i-e employees to achieve excellence and better results. The present study suggested that managers/management of the manufacturing sector may increase intrinsic motivation and job satisfaction of its employees by satisfying and promoting perceived organizational support &extrinsic inspiration in business. Presence of perceived organizational support & extrinsic drive, employees being the most valuable asset for any organization, feel more energetic, encouraged, and motivated to achieve goals and objectives not for the organization only but for themselves as well meaning that they have more enthusiasm, energy, and feeling of being valued and recognition which help them in performing their tasks effectively and also able to achieve challenging goals and objectives.

Moreover, the current study implies that when employees know that these employers regard their efforts and value their welfare, they feel motivated, satisfied, and energized and they are psychologically i-e intrinsically motivated which enhances their job obligation and satisfaction. Principally, organizations need to establish and promote intrinsic motivation of employees to produce a productive work environment because when an organization valued their employees' contributions, employees revert their support to the organization in terms of better performance and effective output. The management can promote perceived organizational support through better SOP, cooperation, and practice conflict resolution whereas extrinsic motivation can be enhanced and promoted through better policies.

Furthermore, results showed that perceived organizational support offers beneficial results and outcomes (employees' engagement, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviors, etc.) (Ahmad et al, 2013; Baran et al, 2012). The educational sector needs to analyze the need for the current dynamic changes and the benefits of perceived organizational support. If an organization desire to make the workforce feel supported, it should provide justice and supportive work culture. The results of this study guide management of the

educational sector to enhance employee motivation and positive work-related attitude through organizational efforts such as a supportive work environment.

Limitation and Future Research

Researchers of the current paper endeavor fair efforts, but it is not free from limitations.

The first one is, data is collected from a primary source, and a unit of analysis is single i.e., employees only which could incur biases and the relationship of the study could be limited (Podsakoff, 2012). Future research can use different sources to collect data.

The second one is, we investigate the impact of POS and EM on JS with mediating role of IM through the cross-sectional design of the study. In such a study design, data is collected only one time which cannot verify the cause, and effect relationship of study variables. To explore a better cause-and-effect relationship between study variables, future research could exploit longitudinal study design.

The third one is, in the present study, data is collected from the shoe manufacturing sector of Lahore Pakistan by using stratified random sampling. Therefore, the results of this study may not truly depict employees that are working in different sectors or cities of Pakistan. To generalize the findings of our study, future researchers could collect data from different sectors.

Fourth, the current attempt is the first unique attempt of researchers that examine the impact of POS and EM on JS with mediating role of IM. Research is carried out in the precise society & working environment of the organization relating to Pakistan. Future studies can endorse the results of the present study in other developed countries due to the fact that each and every country has a different culture and working procedure and Pakistani culture is very different from other developing countries (Malik, Butt, & Choi, 2015).

The fifth one is, in the current study, we examine the IM as a sole mediator between POS and JS. It is possible further, to look into relationships through other extra mediators which may include OC, JS, work engagement, etc. (Hirschler et al., 2014).

Conclusions

Based on the current business scenario, organizations are in an effort to gain high performance and sustainable competitive advantage, POS is an important factor for effective setups. This research adjoins the knowledge of POS through empirical examination of its ancestor and effect in manufacturing sector institutions. The results authenticate that there is a positive and significant connection between hypothesized relationships. It is also confirmed that IM mediates the relationship between POS and JS and also between ES and JS. This research indicates that POS and EM play a vital role in affecting IM and JS toward work. Consequently, in today's taxing scenario, organizations must highlight establishing organizational support in the work environment to make a difference in employee performance psychologically and also in developing EM to enhance employee's positive job attitude as well as motivation, engagement, and satisfaction with the job.

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